

Ensemble of naive Bayes, decision tree, and random forest to predict air quality

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ABSTRACT

Air quality prediction is an important research issue because air quality can affect many areas of life. This study aims to predict air quality using the ensemble method and compare the results with the prediction results using a single method. The proposed ensemble method is built from three single-supervised methods: naïve Bayes, decision trees, and random forests. The results show that the ensemble method performs better than the single methods. The ensemble method achieves the highest performance with scores of 99.89% accuracy, 79.6% precision, 79.81% recall, and 79.7% F1-score. The performance comparison between single and ensemble models is expected to provide information on the percentage increase in predictive model performance metrics from the single to ensemble methods.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, globalization in human activities has greatly affected air quality and climate change at urban, regional, continental, and global levels. The areas most affected are countries with high industrial activity [1]. Meteorological conditions such as humidity, pressure, wind speed, rainfall, temperature, and atmospheric phenomena significantly affect air quality [2]. Air quality forecasting is an appropriate technological method for scientific decision-making and comprehensively maintaining the environment to reinforce air pollution prevention and control. It offers a valuable way to convert relevant environmental monitoring data into a core principle for air pollution mitigation and judgment [3]. Air quality prediction is an important issue nowadays because air quality levels, especially those at dangerous or destructive levels, can affect various areas of human life [4], especially for health and the environment. In its predictions in 2012 alone, the World Health Organization (WHO) found that air pollution contributes to approximately 9% of deaths from lung cancer, 17% due to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, more than 30% due to ischemic heart disease and stroke, and 9% due to respiratory infections [5].

The prediction model that has the best performance is an issue that is no less important. Satisfactory performance of the prediction model is expected to be a reference in carrying out prediction tasks. Some prediction methods only allow the predictor variable to be on a ratio or interval scale. Still, other plans require a nominal or ordinal scale or can be a mixture of these scales. In some cases, the performance of predictive models that apply discretization to numeric type predictor variables can improve model

performance [6], [7], especially in predicting air quality [8]. When the type of predictor variable data owned differs from the characteristics of the method implemented, preprocessing must be done using transformation, normalization, or discretization [9]. Predictor variable discretization is a crucial data preprocessing technology in many applications [10]. Implementing these techniques can also improve the performance of prediction models [11]. Several prediction methods that allow interval or ratio data to be discretized so that they are nominal or ordinal to improve model performance are naïve Bayes (NB), decision trees (DT), and random forest (RF). In other situations, working with categorical data may be for practical reasons [12].

The NB method is based on Bayes theorem and a strong conditional independence assumption between the predictor variables. However, the assumption is rarely valid in real-world applications [13]. The DT method represents a function that maps predictor variable values into a set of classes that represent the allowable hypotheses [14]. This method classifies observations by separating tree branches, where each separation presents a test through a criterion. Each split is called a node, and the first node is called the tree's root. These criteria can vary for each predictor variable [15]. The RF method is an upgrade to bagging pioneered by Breiman in which some classifiers must be used as DT [14].

The three single-supervised methods also provide satisfactory performance in most cases. For example, the implementation of NB in cases of customer sentiment [16], corn plant diseases and pests [13], [17], predicting bank depositor's behavior [18], and diabetes mellitus disease status [19]. Then, implementation of DT in cases of air quality [8], and secure shell (SSH) protocol [20]. Likewise, RF implementation in cases of android malware [21] and rice-leaf disease detection [22]. However, not a few implementations of each method provide unsatisfactory performance. Among them are studies on student performance implementing NB [23], detection of maize leaf disease using DT [24], and admission of new students using RF [25].

An ensemble method with categorical response is an approach that combines several single prediction methods using a voting system to make the final decision [26]–[28]. Combining multiple single learning models has been proven to perform significantly better theoretically and experimentally than the single base learning model [29]. The ensemble method is a statistical and computational learning procedure similar to the human social learning behavior of seeking multiple perspectives before making any vital choice [30]. The ensemble method tends to reduce the variance of classifiers. This method can also improve the generalizability and robustness of a single method [31]–[33]. This method exploits single methods' characteristics to create outstanding performance models [12]. The performance of single-supervised prediction methods can be improved by using the concept of ensemble method [28]. The ensemble method has many real-world applications. However, the problem is the development of a high-performance [34]. Some examples of cases where performance is increased by applying the ensemble method are knowledge discovery datamining (KDD) Cup-99, credit card, Wisconsin prognostic breast cancer (WPBC), forest cover, and PIMA datasets [35], intrusion detection in the industrial internet of things (IIoT) networks [36], indoor WiFi positioning verification, and chronic kidney disease prediction [37]. Each of these studies uses a single method that differs based on experience.

This study aims to predict air quality using the ensemble method and compare the results with the prediction results using a single method. The performance comparison between single and ensemble models is expected to provide information on the percentage increase in predictive model performance metrics from the single to ensemble methods. Likewise, performance comparisons between models implementing all predictor variables and the significant predictor variables are compared. The best prediction results indicated by the model's performance with the highest metric are expected to be a reference in carrying out prediction tasks. In addition, it is hoped that it will be helpful for the government and the community to take policies and actions to reduce/avoid the adverse effects of air quality.

2. METHOD

The data used in this research is air quality data of Shanghai, China, in 2014-2021, obtained from kaggle.com, accessed on August 1st, 2022. This paper discusses Shanghai's air quality because Shanghai has seasonal air conditions, is near the ocean, and has poor air quality. The data consists of 2502 observations with nineteen predictor variables where all the variables are of type numeric. Generally, the variable predictor consists of weather factors ($X_1 - X_9$) and atmospheric variables ($X_{10} - X_{19}$). The target variables representing air quality consist of five classes: hazardous, very unhealthy, unhealthy, unhealthy for sensitive groups, and moderate. The data summary of the predictor variables is given in Table 1.

The research steps are presented in Figure 1. In the early stages, before building a model for training, preprocessing was carried out on the original data by discretizing the predictor variables. The chi-square test is applied to select predictor variables significantly influencing the target variable. They

consider the observations time series data; 2014-2019 (about 70%) were selected as training data, and 2020-2021 (about 30%) as test data.

Table 1. Data summary

Variable	Range	Mean	Standard deviation
Maximum temperature (X_1)	(-3 °C) – 40 °C	21.45	8.51
Minimum temperature (X_2)	(-6 °C) – 3 °C	15.05	8.05
Total snow (X_3)	0 – 1.7 mm	0.00	0.04
Sun hour (X_4)	3.8 h – 14.5 h	9.62	3.13
UV index (X_5)	1 nm– 9 nm	4.69	1.74
Moon illumination (X_6)	0 °C – 100 °C	46.27	31.28
Dew point (X_7)	(-23 °C) – 28 °C	12.92	8.90
Feels like (X_8)	(-9 °C) – 45 °C	19.45	10.48
Heat index (X_9)	(-3 °C) – 45 °C	20.20	9.67
Wind chill (X_{10})	(-9) – 36 °C	18.07	8.79
Wind gust (X_{11})	4 km/h – 82 km/h	17.29	6.67
Cloud cover (X_{12})	0 Okta – 100 Octa	46.63	30.69
Humidity (X_{13})	18% - 97%	71.05	13.36
Precipitation (X_{14})	0 mm – 127 mm	1.84	6.08
Pressure (X_{15})	986 MB – 1039 MB	1016.41	8.93
Temperature (X_{16})	(-3 °C) – 40 °C	21.45	8.51
Visibility (X_{17})	3 m – 20 m	9.54	1.30
Wind dir degree (X_{18})	8° - 347°	153.97	75.99
Wind speed (X_{19})	3-51 km/h	12.64	4.50

Figure 1. Steps of research

NB, DT, and RF are supervised methods for predicting a qualitative response. All three are single methods. Combining these single methods, where the best model performance is obtained using a voting system, is called the ensemble method. The ensemble method with various combinations of single methods has been to obtain better performance than single methods [29]. Numerical experiments also show that the ensemble method is more efficient [26]. This method also helps in averaging biases and reducing the variance of different single methods [28]. We propose the three single methods, NB, DT, and RF, and the ensemble to predict the Shanghai, China, air quality. These single methods predict air quality by involving all predictor variables and are compared with those that only involve significant predictor variables from the

chi-square test results. Eliyati *et al.* [19] only use a single DT method and involve all predictor variables, which are discretized to predict air quality without a variable selection process.

The NB method predicts that an observation is a class member by determining the posterior probability based on the Bayes theorem. This method also requires assumptions of independence and naïve (strong independence) between the variables in calculating conditional probability. When this assumption is not met, the predictor variable of numeric type must be discretized first. Discretization is grouping the values of continuous variables into classes with certain intervals to find categorical type variables [38]. In the crisp set, if an element of universal X is a member of set A , then it is written as $x \in A$. Conversely, if x is not a member of A , it is written as $x \notin A$. So, there are only two possibilities for the membership value of x in set A , $\mu_A(x) = 1$ or $\mu_A(x) = 0$. The crisp discretization forms categories with the specific interval by determining non-overlapping points of intersection. We propose discretization based on the crisp set concerning the characteristics of each variable. The NB method is then constructed using discretized predictor variables. Let Y_j be the random variable that represents the j -th air quality class, $P(Y_j)$ be the j -th air quality class prior probability, $P(X_1, \dots, X_D | Y_j)$ be the likelihood function of D discretized predictor variables, and $P(X_1, \dots, X_D)$ be the likelihood or joint distribution function. Let $n(X_d | Y_j)$ is the number of observations related to the j -th air quality class in all variables X , $n(Y_j)$ is the number of observations in the j -th air quality class, $n_c(X_d | Y_j)$ is the number of observations related to the j -th air quality class in a variable X_d with category k , m is the number of categories in the variable X_d . The j -th class air quality prior probability and the j -th likelihood function with a smoothing parameter α of 1, respectively, are defined as (1) and (2) [19]:

$$P(Y_j) = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^D n(X_d | Y_j) + 1}{n(Y_j) + D} \quad (1)$$

$$P(X_d | Y_j) = \frac{\sum_k n_k(X_d | Y_j) + \alpha}{n(X_d | Y_j) + \alpha m} = \frac{\sum_k n_k(X_d | Y_j) + 1}{n(X_d | Y_j) + m} \quad (2)$$

The posterior probability is given as (3):

$$\begin{aligned} P(Y_j | X_1, \dots, X_D) &= \frac{P(Y_j) P(X_1, \dots, X_D | Y_j)}{P(X_1, \dots, X_D)} \\ &= \frac{P(Y_j) \prod_{d=1}^D P(X_d | Y_j)}{P(X_1, \dots, X_D)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The product of the predictor variables likelihood probability $P(X_1, \dots, X_D)$ is a constant for each class, so the posterior probability is written as (4) [19]:

$$P(Y_j | X_1, \dots, X_D) = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^D n(X_d | Y_j) + 1}{n(Y_j) + D} \prod_{d=1}^D \frac{\sum_k n_k(X_d | Y_j) + 1}{n(X_d | Y_j) + m} \quad (4)$$

In the research data presented in Table 1, all predictor variables are numeric. At the same time, in the NB method, it is necessary to assume a Gaussian distribution for numeric type data. We proposed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test to find out whether the predictor variable in the weather quality data for Shanghai, China, 2014-2021 has a Gaussian distribution. Let x_i is the value of the predictor variable X_i , $F(x_i)$ is the cumulative distribution function, $F(z_i)$ is the standard cumulative normal distribution function Z_i , and n is the sample size [19], [39], [40].

$$KS = \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} (|F(z_i) - F_{n-1}(x_i)|, |F(z_i) - F(x_i)|) \quad (5)$$

The null hypothesis of the inference is that the predictor variable follows a Gaussian distribution. The hypothesis is rejected if the p-value is smaller than the significant level of 5%. DT and RF are tree-based prediction methods. DT is built based on decisions at each node, forming a tree to reach a final decision [14]. At the same time, the final decision in a RF is built based on a combination of decisions from several trees where the variables involved in decision-making are chosen randomly and independently. The selection of random and independent variables in the development of tree-based decisions in RF results in this model being robust and having low bias [41]. Each decision on the DT and RF methods is determined based on the entropy and gain, as presented in (6)-(8). The predictor variable with the highest gain value is used as a node,

and the first node is called the root node. The tree formation starts from the root; the next node is called internal, and the last node that contains class decisions is called the terminal.

Let Y is the response variable that represents the class of air quality, X_d is the independent variable that represents the factors affecting air quality, p_j is the prior probability in the j -th class of Y , and p_m is the prior probability in the m -th category of X_d . We also let that $k(Y)$ is the number of classes in Y , $k(X_d)$ is the number of categories in X_d , $S(Y)$ is the number of observations in all types Y , and $S(X_d^m)$ is the number of observations in the m -th category. The entropy of the response and the independent variables are written successively as (6) and (7):

$$H(S(Y)) = - \sum_{j=1}^{k(Y)} p_j \log_2 p_j \tag{6}$$

$$H(X_d^m) = - \sum_{m=1}^{k(X_d)} p_m \log_2 p_m \tag{7}$$

The gain of (Y, X_d) is expressed as (8):

$$G(Y, X_d) = H(S(Y)) - \sum_{m=1}^{k(X_d)} \frac{S(X_d^m)}{S(Y)} H(X_d^m) \tag{8}$$

An ensemble is a set of classifiers whose individual decisions are combined somehow, typically by weighted or unweighted voting to classification. Ensemble methods combine multiple single methods to obtain the best performance in prediction or classification tasks [29]. The ensemble method trains several models and combines them using boosting and bagging techniques [32]. Boosting is a process that transforms a flawed learning model into a good learning model. Bagging applies the bootstrap sampling method to generate multiple data sets for training. The final decision is obtained using majority voting [28]. This voting system can reduce covariance and avoid overfitting [27].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Data exploration and processing

This study's initial data exploration stage was testing the Gaussian assumptions on all predictor variables. There are three general procedures for testing Gaussian assumptions: Q-Q diagrams, histograms, and numerical methods (statistical tests), with the latter being the most formal. Kolmogorov-Smirnov is a powerful statistical test for this purpose. Table 2 presents the results of the Gaussian assumption test with $\alpha=5\%$ using Kolmogorov-Smirnov.

Table 2. Gaussian assumption test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov

Variable	stat	p-value
Maximum temperature (X_1)	0.08	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Minimum temperature (X_2)	0.08	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Total snow (X_3)	0.51	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Sun hour (X_4)	0.12	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
UV index (X_5)	0.13	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Moon illumination (X_6)	0.07	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Dew point (X_7)	0.09	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Feels like (X_8)	0.07	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Heat index (X_9)	0.08	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Wind chill (X_{10})	0.10	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Wind gust (X_{11})	0.10	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Cloud cover (X_{12})	0.08	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Humidity (X_{13})	0.06	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Precipitation (X_{14})	0.38	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Pressure (X_{15})	0.08	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Temperature (X_{16})	0.08	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Visibility (X_{17})	0.35	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Wind dir degree (X_{18})	0.07	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Wind speed (X_{19})	0.10	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$

The test results show that all predictor variables have a p-value $< \alpha$, so it can be concluded that these variables do not have a Gaussian distribution. The results of testing predictor variables in various cases generally show the same conclusions, such as the distribution of predictor variables in the classification of diseases and pests in corn plants [17], or prediction of diabetes status [19]. It is generally challenging to find

all predictor variables with a Gaussian distribution [42]. However, testing the assumptions is still necessary so they are not mistaken in the subsequent data processing, including in the analysis stage. Furthermore, this study explores the correlation between predictor variables to accommodate naïve assumptions in the NB method as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Correlation between the predictor variable

Based on Figure 2, it can be concluded that naïve assumptions can be used because the variables with a strong correlation are not more than 50%. Weak relationships between variables may indicate that they are not interdependent. In other words, this fact supports the naïve assumption. Furthermore, because all predictor variables do not have a Gaussian distribution, the data is normalized first before the air quality of Shanghai, China, is predicted using the NB, DT, and RF methods, respectively. The data can also be discretized, but specifically for categorical data, the NB method has a particular name, multinomial NB. At the same time, the DT method is the ID3 algorithm.

Figure 3 shows the discretization result of each predictor variable in the Shanghai city air quality data. The discretization is created based on each variable's characteristics and value range, as presented in Table 1. The predictor variables indicating weather factors are given in Figures 3(a)-3(i), while indicating atmospheric phenomena in Figures 3(j)-3(s). In Figure 3(a), the maximum temperature variable is discretized into cold (0 °C-20.4 °C), cool (20.5-23.9 °C), warm (24-29.9 °C), hot (30-37.9 °C), and very hot (>38 °C). Figure 3(b) shows minimum temperature variable is discretized into freezing (<-0.1 °C), cold (0-20.4 °C), cool (20.5-23.9 °C), warm (24-29.9 °C), hot (30-37.9 °C), and very hot (>38 °C). Total snow, as presented in Figure 3(c), is discretized into very little (0-0.33 mm), moderate (0.68-1.01 mm), and very much (>1.36 mm). Figure 3(d) discretizes sun hour into very little (3.9-5.93 hour), little (5.94-8.07 hour), moderate (8.08-10.21 hour), a lot (10.22-12.35 hour), and very much (>12.36 hour). UV index, as shown in Figure 3(e), discretized the data into low (1-2.9 nm), medium (3-5.9 nm), high (6-7.9 nm), and very high (8-10.9 nm). The variable of moon illumination in Figure 3(f) discretizes the data into very low (0-19.9 °C), low (20-39.9 °C), moderate (40-59.9 °C), high (60-79.9 °C), and very high (>80 °C). Figure 3(g) presents discretization of dew point variable into very dry (<-0.1 °C), comfortable dry air (0-9.9 °C), very comfortable (10-12.9 °C), comfortable (13-15.9 °C), slightly uncomfortable (16-17.9 °C), moderately uncomfortable (18-20.9 °C), very uncomfortable (21-23.9 °C), and extremely uncomfortable (>24 °C). In Figure 3(h) feels like variable is discretized into very low (<1.7 °C), low (1.8-12.5 °C), moderate (12.6-23.3 °C), high (23.4-34.1 °C), and very high (>34.2 °C). Figure 3(i) shows that the heat index variable is discretized into very low (<26.6 °C), low (26.7-32.1 °C), moderate (32.2-39.3 °C), and high (>34.2 °C).

Figure 3. Discretized data: (a) maximum temperature, (b) minimum temperature, (c) total snow, (d) sun hour, (e) uv index, (f) moon illumination, (g) dew point, (h) feels like, (i) heat index, (j) wind chill, (k) wind gust, (l) cloud cover, (m) humidity, (n) precipitation, (o) pressure, (p) temperature, (q) visibility, (r) wind direction, and (s) wind speed

Wind chill variable in Figure 3(j) is discretized into very low ($<0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$), low ($0-0.33^{\circ}\text{C}$), normal ($0.34-0.67^{\circ}\text{C}$), high ($0.68-1.01^{\circ}\text{C}$), and very high ($>1.02^{\circ}\text{C}$). Variable of wind gust in Figure 3(k) discretize the data into little calm ($1-5\text{ km/h}$), a little blow ($6-11\text{ km/h}$), gentle breeze ($12-19\text{ km/h}$), moderate breeze ($20-29\text{ km/h}$), and cool breeze ($30-39\text{ km/h}$). Figure 3(l) shows cloud cover variable is discretized into bright ($0-20\text{ octa}$), generally sunny ($21-40\text{ octa}$), partly cloudy ($41-60\text{ octa}$), generally cloudy ($61-80\text{ octa}$), and overcast ($>81\text{ octa}$). Humidity variable, as presented in Figure 3(m), is discretized into too dry ($0-39\%$), ideal ($40-69\%$), and too moist ($>70\%$). Figure 3(n) shows precipitation variable is discretized into cloudy ($<0\text{ mm}$), light rain ($1-20\text{ mm}$), moderate ($21-50\text{ mm}$), heavy rain ($51-100\text{ mm}$), and very heavy ($>101\text{ mm}$). In Figure 3(o), the pressure variable is discretized into very low ($986-996.5\text{ mb}$), low ($996.6-998.73\text{ mb}$), moderate ($998.74-1000.87\text{ mb}$), high ($1000.88-1003.01\text{ MB}$), and very high ($>1003.02\text{ MB}$). Figure 3(p) shows optimum temperature variable is discretized into very cold ($<-0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$), cold ($0-20.4^{\circ}\text{C}$), cool ($20.5-23.9^{\circ}\text{C}$), warm ($24-29.9^{\circ}\text{C}$), hot ($30-37.9^{\circ}\text{C}$), and very hot ($>38^{\circ}\text{C}$). Visibility variable in Figure 3(q) is discretized into dense fog ($0.03-0.15\text{ m}$), moderate fog ($0.16-0.53\text{ m}$), very light fog ($0.54-1.07\text{ m}$), light mist ($1.08-2.15\text{ m}$), and very light misc ($2.16-5.3\text{ m}$). Variable of wind direction degree in Figure 3(r) discretizes the data into north ($0-23^{\circ}$), north east ($24-68^{\circ}$), east ($69-113^{\circ}$), south east ($114-158^{\circ}$), south ($159-203^{\circ}$), south west ($204-248^{\circ}$), west ($249-293^{\circ}$), north west ($294-336^{\circ}$), and north ($>337^{\circ}$). Figure 3(s) shows wind speed variable is discretized into light air ($1-3\text{ km/h}$), light breeze ($4-7\text{ km/h}$), gentle breeze ($8-12\text{ km/h}$), moderate breeze ($13-18\text{ km/h}$), fresh breeze ($19-24\text{ km/h}$), strong breeze ($25-31\text{ km/h}$), moderate gale ($32-38\text{ km/h}$), and fresh gale ($39-46\text{ km/h}$).

The discretization result does not produce a balanced distribution of observations in each category on each predictor variable. The distribution imbalance of each extreme category due to discretization based on the characteristics of this variable can be found in the variables total snow (X_3), heat index (X_9), wind chill (X_{10}), pressure (X_{15}), and visibility (X_{17}). However, the imbalance in the distribution of each category on these predictor variables does not affect the significance of the response variable.

Furthermore, this study proposes the chi-squared test to determine the effect of discretized predictor variables on the target variable. Table 3 shows the results of the chi-squared test where the two predictor variables, total snow (X_3) and moon illumination (X_6) do not affect the target variable. In the next stage of the prediction process, the existence of these two variables has a different effect on the performance of each prediction model.

Table 3. Chi-square test

Variable	Chi-square	df	p-value
Maximum temperature (X_1)	10008.00	16	0.00
Minimum temperature (X_2)	3227.40	16	0.00
Total snow (X_3)	4.94	8	0.76
Sun hour (X_4)	1148.08	16	2.06×10^{-234}
UV index (X_5)	2221.82	12	0.00
Moon illumination (X_6)	24.34	16	0.08
Dew point (X_7)	3168.70	28	0.00
Feels like (X_8)	3270.11	16	0.00
Heat index (X_9)	2745.12	12	0.00
Wind chill (X_{10})	107.08	12	2.26×10^{-17}
Wind gust (X_{11})	146.12	24	1.73×10^{-19}
Cloud cover (X_{12})	199.83	16	8.60×10^{-34}
Humidity (X_{13})	135.46	8	2.08×10^{-25}
Precipitation (X_{14})	23.34	8	2.95×10^{-03}
Pressure (X_{15})	308.78	16	3.86×10^{-56}
Temperature (X_{16})	10008	16	0.00
Visibility (X_{17})	12.56	4	0.01
Wind dir degree (X_{18})	300.09	32	2.56×10^{-45}
Wind speed (X_{19})	95.60	28	2.58×10^{-09}

3.2. Prediction of the air quality

Air quality for Shanghai data is predicted into five classes: hazardous, very unhealthy, unhealthy, unhealthy for sensitive groups, and moderate. The prediction results are evaluated based on the confusion matrix for multiclass problems using four metrics, namely accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score [43], [44]. NB, DT, and RF are implemented into two models for each single method. The first model includes all predictor variables, and the second only involves significant variables based on the chi-square test. The performance of the two models for each single method is presented in Table 4.

In the NB method, the prediction model's performance involving only significant variables increases compared to the model involving all variables. The increase occurred in all four metrics as measured by different percentages. However, it is inversely proportional to the DT and RF methods, where the prediction

model's performance involving only significant variables is not higher than the model involving all variables, also on the four metrics measured with different percentages. From the six models presented in Table 4, it can be seen that the RF method with a model involving all variables is the model with the best performance compared to the other five models. This fact shows that in this case, although the performance of the NB model involving significant variables is not better than the DT and RF models, including only significant variables in the prediction can improve the performance of the NB method. The four proposed models using the supervised single methods have good accuracy (except two models of NB), more than 85% [45], but the other three performance metrics are below 85%.

Table 4. The prediction performance of single methods

Metric	Performance of proposed model (%)					
	NB		DT		RF	
	All variable	Significant variable	All variable	Significant variable	All variable	Significant variable
Accuracy	78.02	78.23	99.05	96.91	99.15	97.39
Precision	27.30	31.10	78.59	72.22	78.20	74.66
Recall	32.97	33.15	77.46	74.66	78.34	74.04
F1-score	29.87	32.09	78.02	73.42	78.27	74.35

Furthermore, the performance of the ensemble model for both models is presented in Table 5. The performance of each ensemble method is better than the single methods, but the other three performance metrics are still below 85%. Ensemble methods that involve all variables in a single method that supports it have better performance than those with only significant variables. This event naturally occurs because two of the three single methods that support the ensemble method with models involving all variables perform better than models involving only significant variables. The performance of a single model that supports the ensemble method dramatically influences the performance of the ensemble model.

Table 5. The prediction performance of the ensemble method

Metric	Performance of proposed model (%)	
	All variable	Significant variable
Accuracy	99.89	97.51
Precision	79.60	74.58
Recall	79.81	74.44
F1-score	79.70	74.51

3.3. Performance comparison

Comparison with other research is presented in Tables 6 to 9, which each presents the performance of three single and ensemble methods. In general, the NB implementation in various cases has good performance metrics, especially accuracy, but the precision value is not always directly proportional to the accuracy value. Good NB model performance is usually obtained because each category spreads the predictor variable discretization evenly. Compared with the performance of the NB prediction method in Table 4, which predicts air quality in the proposed model, with the performance of the NB method in Table 6, the performance of the NB in Table 4 is unsatisfactory, especially on precision, recall, and F1 score metrics. The possible cause is discretization, that is formed unevenly in each category. There are even categories with no observations, thus affecting the probability calculation for each class. Other discretization techniques are needed to get better NB performance. Even discretization in each category in a variable in each class allows for good model performance, as achieved by previous researchers.

Table 6. The performance comparing of the NB

Research (dataset)	Performance metric (%)		
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Kaushik <i>et al.</i> [15] (customer sentiment)	94.00	93.00	94.00
Resti <i>et al.</i> [16] (corn plant disease and pest)	97.72	79.88	79.24
Safarkhani and Moro [17] (bank depositor's behavior)	90.82	-	96.10
Resti <i>et al.</i> [18] (diabetes mellitus disease)	95.83	93.82	94.48
Agghey <i>et al.</i> [20] (username enumeration attack)	95.70	94.85	-
Akbar <i>et al.</i> [21] (android malware)	89.52	89.53	89.52

Table 7. The performance comparing of DT

Research (dataset)	Performance metric (%)		
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Resti <i>et al.</i> [46] (corn plant disease and pest)	94.53	84.31	83.07
Agghey <i>et al.</i> [20] (username enumeration attack)	99.88	99.84	-
Eliyati <i>et al.</i> [19] (air quality of Shanghai)	99.05	78.59	77.46
Panigrahi <i>et al.</i> [24] (maize leaf disease)	74.35	73.00	74.00

Table 8. The performance comparing RF

Research (dataset)	Performance metric (%)		
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Akbar <i>et al.</i> [21] (android malware)	89.96	89.97	89.96
Musaddiq <i>et al.</i> [23] (student's performance)	88.80	89.00	88.00
Agghey <i>et al.</i> [20] (username enumeration attack)	99.92	99.87	-
Singh <i>et al.</i> [22] (rice plant leaf disease)	100.00	100.00	100.00
Nurhachita and Negara [25] (admission of the new student)	44.65	-	-

Table 9. Performance comparison of the ensemble method is higher than the single method

Research (dataset)	Ensemble of methods	Accuracy
Gaurav <i>et al.</i> [37] (chronic kidney disease)	SVM, C45, PSO-MLP, DT	92.76
Tinh and Mai [31] (indoor WIFI positioning)	RF, KNN, DNN	98.90
Elmahalwy <i>et al.</i> [35] (KDD Cup-99)	Isolation Forest & IForest-KMeans	99.70
Elmahalwy <i>et al.</i> [35] (credit card)		97.54
Elmahalwy <i>et al.</i> [35] (WPBC)		97.07
Elmahalwy <i>et al.</i> [35] (forest cover)		94.00
Elmahalwy <i>et al.</i> [35] (Pima)		94.24
Awotunde <i>et al.</i> [36] (IIOT networks of fridge sensor)	RF, Extra Tree, AdaBoost, Bagging	98.73
Awotunde <i>et al.</i> [36] (IIOT networks of the thermostat)		98.83
Awotunde <i>et al.</i> [36] (IIOT networks of GPS tracker)		98.69
Awotunde <i>et al.</i> [36] (IIOT networks of Modbus)		99.13

As with NB, in general, the implementation of DT in various cases as shown in Table 7 has good performance metrics, especially accuracy. However, the precision and recall values are sometimes not directly proportional to the accuracy values. The performance of the DT method in predicting air quality in the proposed models provided very satisfactory performance (accuracy) (more than 96%) in both models in Table 4. This fact indicates that the DT method does not require data normalization, considering that the DT method is nonparametric. In addition, the DT method is more resistant to the distribution of observations that are not evenly distributed in each class.

Rarely does RF implementation in various cases have poor performance metrics, but this does not mean such cases do not exist as shown in Table 8. The RF implementation on the admission of the new student shows an accuracy performance of less than 45% [25]. However, like the other two methods, the precision and recall values are not always directly proportional to the accuracy values. Generally, this event occurs in multiclass cases with unequal class proportions. Other experiments are needed to improve these two metrics, for example, by resampling techniques [13], [46]. Compared with the prediction performance of air quality in the proposed single methods, the RF is the best method in both models, with all variables and the significant variables only. The proposed RF has good accuracy, most above 97%.

Table 9 presents the performance of the ensemble method in some datasets. In the chronic kidney disease (CKD) dataset, the performance of the ensemble method, especially the accuracy, has increased compared to the accuracy of all single methods. The accuracy of the single method for the CKD dataset from lowest to highest is 64.5% SVM, 72.67% DT, 75.32% C4.5, and 86.31% particle swarm optimization-multilayer perceptron (PSO-MLP). In this case, the accuracy increased significantly compared to the single method, around 6.45% - 28.26%. Likewise, for the indoor WIFI positioning dataset, bank bankruptcy, KDD Cup-99, credit card, WPBC, forest cover, Pima datasets, fridge sensor, thermostat, GPS tracker, and Modbus datasets. For the indoor Wifi positioning dataset [31], the accuracy of the single method from lowest to highest is 98.35 k-nearest neighbor (KNN), 98.5% RF, and 98.7% deep neural networks (DNN). The three proposed methods have good accuracy (more than 98%), but the ensemble method has a higher accuracy. The majority of IForest-Kmeans accuracy is higher than isolation forest. The increase in the ensemble method ranges from 2.23% (KDD cup-99 dataset) to 33.43% (credit card dataset) [35]. In the intrusion of IIoT datasets [36], only the Adaboost method has low accuracy. The other three methods have accuracy that competes with the proposed ensemble method. Accuracy for networks of fridge sensor, thermostat, GPS tracker, and Modbus are 98.43%, 98.65%, 98.13%, 98.78% (RF), 98.01%, 98.38%, 97.66%, 98.78% (extra

tree ET)), 48.09% respectively, 53.05%, 47.38%, 62.92% (AdaBoost), and 98.56%, 98.58%, 98.32%, 98.90% (Bagging). Globally, the increase in the ensemble method ranges from 0.35% (Modbus dataset) to 51.31% (GPS tracker).

4. CONCLUSION

This study predicts the air quality of Shanghai using the ensemble method. The method is built based on single methods consisting of NB, DT, and RF methods. Two models are proposed for each single and ensemble method. The conclusion of this study consists of two points. First, selecting significant predictor variables on the response variable using the chi-square test positively impacts the performance of the NB method, but not so with the other two single methods, DT, and RF. Second, the ensemble method has succeeded in improving the performance of a single method in both models, involving all variables and only significant variables. However, the performance of the ensemble method for models involving all variables is better on the four performance-metrics for multiclass. The best prediction results indicated by the model's performance with the highest metric are expected to be a reference in carrying out prediction tasks. In addition, it is hoped that it will be helpful for the government and the community to take policies and actions to reduce/avoid the adverse effects of air quality.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Yan, Y. Li, M. Sun, and Z. Wu, "Primary pollutants and air quality analysis for urban air in china: evidence from Shanghai," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 8, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11082319.
- [2] S. Zeng and Y. Zhang, "The effect of meteorological elements on continuing heavy air pollution: a case study in the chengdu area during the 2014 spring festival," *Atmosphere*, vol. 8, no. 4, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.3390/atmos8040071.
- [3] J. Cai, X. Dai, L. Hong, Z. Gao, and Z. Qiu, "An air quality prediction model based on a noise reduction self-coding deep network," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2020, pp. 1–12, May 2020, doi: 10.1155/2020/3507197.
- [4] M. Jia *et al.*, "Regional air quality forecast using a machine learning method and the WRF model over the yangtze river delta, east China," *Aerosol and Air Quality Research*, vol. 19, no. 7, pp. 1602–1613, 2019, doi: 10.4209/aaqr.2019.05.0275.
- [5] P. Mannucci and M. Franchini, "Health effects of ambient air pollution in developing countries," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 14, no. 9, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.3390/ijerph14091048.
- [6] Y. Pan, H. Gao, H. Lin, Z. Liu, L. Tang, and S. Li, "Identification of bacteriophage virion proteins using multinomial naïve Bayes with g-gap feature tree," *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, vol. 19, no. 6, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.3390/ijms19061779.
- [7] J. Dougherty, R. Kohavi, and M. Sahami, "Supervised and unsupervised discretization of continuous features," *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 1995*, pp. 194–202, 1995, doi: 10.1016/b978-1-55860-377-6.50032-3.
- [8] S. García, J. Luengo, and F. Herrera, "Data preprocessing in data mining," *Intelligent Systems Reference Library*, Cham: Springer, vol. 72, 2015.
- [9] Q. Chen and M. Huang, "Rough fuzzy model-based feature discretization in intelligent data preprocess," *Journal of Cloud Computing*, vol. 10, no. 1, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1186/s13677-020-00216-4.
- [10] A. Podvieszko and V. Podvezko, "Influence of data transformation on multicriteria evaluation result," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 122, pp. 151–157, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2015.10.019.
- [11] M. Kuhn and K. Johnson, *Applied predictive modeling*. New York: Springer, 2013, doi: 10.1007/978-1-4614-6849-3.
- [12] Y. Resti, C. Irsan, A. Neardiaty, C. Annabila, and I. Yani, "Fuzzy discretization on the multinomial naïve bayes method for modeling multiclass classification of corn plant diseases and pests," *Mathematics*, vol. 11, no. 8, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.3390/math11081761.
- [13] A. Altay and D. Cinar, "Fuzzy decision trees," *Fuzzy Statistical Decision-Making*, 2016, pp. 221–261. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-39014-7_13.
- [14] I. H. Witten, E. Frank, and M. A. Hall, *Data mining: practical machine learning tools and techniques*, Burlington, USA: Elsevier, 2011.
- [15] K. Kaushik *et al.*, "Multinomial naïve bayesian classifier framework for systematic analysis of smart IoT devices," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 19, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22197318.
- [16] Y. Resti, C. Irsan, M. T. Putri, I. Yani, Anshori, and B. Suprihatin, "Identification of corn plant diseases and pests based on digital images using multinomial naïve bayes and k-nearest neighbor," *Science and Technology Indonesia*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 29–35, 2022, doi: 10.26554/sti.2022.7.1.29-35.
- [17] F. Safarkhani and S. Moro, "Improving the accuracy of predicting bank depositor's behavior using a decision tree," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 19, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3390/app11199016.
- [18] Y. Resti, E. S. Kresnawati, N. R. Dewi, D. A. Zayanti, and N. Eliyati, "Diagnosis of diabetes mellitus in women of reproductive age using the prediction methods of naïve Bayes, discriminant analysis, and logistic regression," *Science and Technology Indonesia*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 96–104, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.26554/STI.2021.6.2.96-104.
- [19] N. Eliyati, M. Rahmayani, S. Wijaya, D. A. Zayanti, E. S. Kresnawati, and Y. Resti, "Prediction of air quality index using decision tree with discretization," *Indonesian Journal of Engineering and Science*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 61–67, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.51630/ijes.v3i3.82.
- [20] A. Z. Agghey, L. J. Mwinuka, S. M. Pandhare, M. A. Dida, and J. D. Ndibwile, "Detection of username enumeration attack on ssh protocol: Machine learning approach," *Symmetry*, vol. 13, no. 11, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3390/sym13112192.

- [21] F. Akbar, M. Hussain, R. Mumtaz, Q. Riaz, A. W. A. Wahab, and K.-H. Jung, "Permissions-based detection of android malware using machine learning," *Symmetry*, vol. 14, no. 4, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.3390/sym14040718.
- [22] A. K. Singh, B. Chourasia, N. Raghuwanshi, and R. K., "BPSO based feature selection for rice plant leaf disease detection with random forest classifier," *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 34–43, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V69I4P206.
- [23] M. H. Musaddiq, M. S. Sarfraz, N. Shafi, R. Maqsood, A. Azam, and M. Ahmad, "Predicting the impact of academic key factors and spatial behaviors on students' performance," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 19, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/app121910112.
- [24] K. P. Panigrahi, H. Das, A. K. Sahoo, and S. C. Moharana, "Maize leaf disease detection and classification using machine learning algorithms," *Progress in Computing, Analytics and Networking: Proceedings of ICCAN 2019*, 2020, pp. 659–669. doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-2414-1_66.
- [25] N. Nurhachita and E. S. Negara, "A comparison between deep learning, naïve Bayes and random forest for the application of data mining on the admission of new students," *IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence (IJ-AI)*, vol. 10, no. 2, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijai.v10.i2.pp324-331.
- [26] I. E. Livieris, A. Kanavos, V. Tampakas, and P. Pintelas, "A weighted voting ensemble self-labeled algorithm for the detection of lung abnormalities from X-rays," *Algorithms*, vol. 12, no. 3, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.3390/A12030064.
- [27] S. Karlos, G. Kostopoulos, and S. Kotsiantis, "a soft-voting ensemble based co-training scheme using static selection for binary classification problems," *Algorithms*, vol. 13, no. 1, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3390/a13010026.
- [28] S. Dutt, S. Chandramouli, and A. K. Das, *Machine learning*. India: Pearson India Education Service Pvt. Ltd, 2016.
- [29] P. Pintelas and I. E. Livieris, "Special issue on ensemble learning and applications," *Algorithms*, vol. 13, no. 6, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.3390/A13060140.
- [30] R. Matteo and V. Giorgio, "Ensemble methods: a review," *Data Mining and Machine Learning for Astronomical Applications*, pp. 3–40, 2012.
- [31] D. T. Pham and T. T. N. Mai, "Ensemble learning model for Wifi indoor positioning systems," *IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence (IJ-AI)*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 200, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijai.v10.i1.pp200-206.
- [32] Z. H. Zhou, *Ensemble methods: foundations and algorithms*, Boca Raton, Florida: Chapman & Hall/CRC, 2012, doi: 10.1201/b12207.
- [33] J. Ha, M. Kambe, and J. Pe, *Data mining: concepts and techniques*. Morgan Kaufmann, 2011. doi: 10.1016/C2009-0-61819-5.
- [34] C. Zhang and Y. Ma, *Ensemble machine learning: methods and applications*, New York: Springer Publishing, 2012, doi: 10.1007/9781441993267.
- [35] A. M. Elmahalwy, H. M. Mousa, and K. M. Amin, "New hybrid ensemble method for anomaly detection in data science," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 3498-3508, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijecev13i3.pp3498-3508.
- [36] J. B. Awotunde, C. Chakraborty, and A. E. Adeniyi, "Intrusion detection in industrial internet of things network-based on deep learning model with rule-based feature selection," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–17, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/7154587.
- [37] K. Gaurav, D. A. Naik, V. K. Jaiswal, A. M. and A. V., "Chronic kidney disease prediction," *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1065–1069, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.26438/ijcse/v7i4.10651069.
- [38] M. Shanmugapriya, H. K. Nehemiah, R. S. Bhuvaneshwaran, K. Arputharaj, and J. D. Sweetlin, "Fuzzy discretization based classification of medical data," *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 14, no. 8, pp. 291–298, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.19026/rjaset.14.4953.
- [39] N. M. Razali and Y. B. Wah, "Power comparisons of shapiro-wilk, kolmogorov-smirnov, lilliefors and anderson-darling tests," *Journal of Statistical Modeling and Analytics*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 13–14, 2011.
- [40] G. J. Székely and M. L. Rizzo, "A new test for multivariate normality," *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, vol. 93, no. 1, pp. 58–80, Mar. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.jmva.2003.12.002.
- [41] D. Conn, T. Ngung, G. Li, and C. M. Ramirez, "Fuzzy forests: extending random forest feature selection for correlated, high-dimensional data," *Journal of Statistical Software*, vol. 91, no. 9, 2019, doi: 10.18637/jss.v091.i09.
- [42] M. Hallin and D. Paindaveine, "Optimal tests for homogeneity of covariance, scale, and shape," *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, vol. 100, no. 3, pp. 422–444, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.jmva.2008.05.010.
- [43] S. Dinesh and T. Dash, "Reliable evaluation of neural network for multiclass classification of real-world data," *Arxiv-Computer Science*, pp. 1-6, Nov. 2016.
- [44] M. Sokolova and G. Lapalme, "A systematic analysis of performance measures for classification tasks," *Information Processing & Management*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 427–437, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ipm.2009.03.002.
- [45] S. Aronoff, "Classification accuracy: a user approach.," *Photogrammetric Engineering and Remote Sensing*, vol. 48, no. 8, pp. 1299–1307, 1982.
- [46] Y. Resti, C. Irsan, M. Amini, I. Yani, R. Passarella, and D. A. Zayantii, "Performance improvement of decision tree model using fuzzy membership function for classification of corn plant diseases and pests," *Science and Technology Indonesia*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 284–290, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.26554/sti.2022.7.3.284-290.

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